

Variation and dialogic communication in maths teacher education in a multilingual context: A response to Anthony Essien

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Anthony Essien, in his plenary session, presented a triadic Framework to analyse the choice of “exemplification” in teachers education mathematics classrooms in a multilingual context, with a focus on the role of the teacher educator, who is seldom the object of research in education. In my response, I will be reviewing his paper on two counts. A. I will be reflecting on the presentation of the triadic framework developed and B. reviewing how the selection of examples and the classroom interaction can be further extended to bring a greater multilingual and multi-cultural input into maths teacher education, with a greater focus on dialogue. I will end with a few suggestions as to how the framework may be extended and enriched to incorporate multilinguality in a stronger way.

The triadic framework for analysing choice of examples

As the elements of choice of examples in a multilingual mathematics classroom are complex, choice is determined by complex interrelated factors. A framework putting together these elements that can act as criteria of choice, is, indeed, important. It is, heartening that Anthony has taken upon himself this challenging task.

Another important aspect is that the site for the framework is teacher education classrooms and not school classrooms. This is a crucial element that is often neglected. Even though we're talking of Student Teachers here, the assumption that the student teacher has understood school mathematics concepts does not hold for developing countries like South Africa and India.

It is in the context of recognising its importance and its strengths that I now critique it. Maths is a subject that takes one through to an abstract realm. However, the human mind learns through concrete examples, from experience and reflections. Hence, exemplification is a necessary part of learning. It is interesting that Anthony tries to see “exemplification” through trying to make a triad of three different yet inter - related frameworks. This is an important exercise. He has chosen to do it theoretically rather than empirically. In the attempt to develop this framework theoretically, the elements of the framework have not been explicated enough and have become somewhat opaque. A little more elaboration with examples would have been more helpful.

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The triadic framework developed by merging variation theory, the dialogic interactive communicative process and the multifaceted aspects of multilingual contexts has captured a lot of important aspects and placed them in relation to each other. However, it seems to put multilingual aspects and contexts as an add on at the end, whereas this needs to be an integral and overarching part of the framework – like a canvas in a painting. Because language and multilinguality is what is the lifeblood of the children learning the mathematics.

The paper does not deal with the language aspects and its relation to mathematization at all. This is an important weakness. Different languages not only have different words, but different idioms and cultural contexts that need to be taken into account. A more centre-stage position to multilingualism would have brought out the immense potential of intertwining it with variation theory. This would map the examples from different languages and cultures onto the critical features of a mathematical concept and procedure.

Variation and dialogue: Two important elements for maths education in a multilingual context

The element of variation, in mathematics classrooms has two aspects to it – a) content variation and b) procedural variation. The latter is equally, if not more important in mathematization of concepts, but has not been dealt with at all. Procedural variation gives a lot of scope for multilingual and multi-cultural ways of solving problems, particularly oral ways – classical examples are using grouped addition from hundreds to units for multiplication – rather than the written algorithm of multiplying from the unit side and carrying over – this is procedural variation and is present in almost all algorithms. If connected with multilingual cultures, it would give a lot of mathematical power to deprived communities, whose procedural variations are excluded from mainstream mathematics.

Equally important are the communication and dialogue aspects, which have not been elaborated – the collective, reciprocal, supportive, cumulative and purposeful aspects of dialogue. It is not only language that is different in a multilingual context, but the cultural differences reflected by the language are much deeper and wider.

Those tribes and community groups that have developed with livelihoods which interact with numbers in certain ways, often give rise to quinary, quinary-decimal and vigesimal number systems in traditional societies. Even though other aspects of tribal living may decline – sometimes, when the livelihood remains the same, such number systems, ways of calculations, words, phrases, riddles continue. They make for a stronger procedure in the heads of such communities than the formal metric system introduced through school. Incorporating these in the examples and dialogues in the classroom has a number of advantages.

1. Most such groups are deprived communities and their language and ways of thinking have been excluded from the mainstream classroom. This invisibilises them, undermines their identity and demotivates them from continuing their studies. Including conceptual and procedural variation on mathematisation from their lives, will enhance their visibility and motivate them to learn mathematics better and own that learning.

A. Noronha

2. A diversity of variations will also help other students in class become familiar with a greater diversity of possibilities, other cultures and other words and meanings. This will develop cognitive robustness as well as empathy in all students.

Using the triadic framework to understand examples in multilingual mathematics classrooms

The concept chosen is an introduction to probability. While it is mentioned that the language background of the teacher educator and the student teachers is different, it is not clear which languages, tribes and cultures the student teachers hail from.

The choice of the four examples is mentioned, but not the bases of their choice. It is not clear whether they have been contributed by the student teachers, or the teacher educator decided on them by himself. Enough background is not available to say how they were chosen and any links to the cultures and languages of the student teachers are not mentioned. Football, dice games and cards all seem western contexts.

The aspect of probability being dependent on ambient conditions on a large scale is not mentioned nor incorporated in the activity or dialogue, or how this probability can be played around with – weighting the dice or coin. Just discussing one example does not bring out the conceptual and contextual features.

The teacher educator in the transcript excerpt also doesn't give ample space to discussing the student teachers' own conceptual, cultural ideas on probability and reveal their own language of probability. I don't know enough about South Africa, but in India the idea of probability is integrally linked with the idea of fate. Another area is gambling. We, in our alternative science curriculum have taken up the issue of odds in gambling, at the middle school level, and shown how it is impossible to have a winning situation in the end.

Secondly, this example did not have much dialogue or real interaction, somewhat vitiating the point of the dialogue part of the framework. It was presented by the TE in a relatively closed ended way – the coin was not tossed even once in the excerpt, whereas to get a hang of probability – you need to toss it a fairly large number of times, then go to the numerator denominator issue. Had it been followed up by a number of throws, the name for the throws, the use of coin throwing discussed, it may have brought forth a better dialogue necessary for better understanding. As presented both the activity and dialogue seem cosmetic rather than authentic.

A lot of mathematics – number, operations, time, weight, length, algebra can be dealt with in a multilingual way, using variation of examples and procedures from different cultures. This would benefit both the different language speakers as well as the dominant language speakers as through dialogue they could collectively bring consonance. This would require a framework for multilinguality which maps on to the variation theory framework.

In conclusion

In order to integrate a framework for multilinguality along with variation theory and communication, elements of language and culture, that could form criteria for selection of examples need to be laid out.

Some of these could be

- Words and phrases closest to the concept, that are available in the learners' context (e.g., number names in a quinary system, how number names for larger numbers are constructed in the language, or names for units of time, weight distance, etc., and for past, future, long short).
- Real life contexts where the concept is used (e.g., when teaching percentages look for examples of percentage in the community and how it is expressed – e.g., in poor communities and rural contexts when in the context of lending the phrase x rs. *prati saikda* (per hundred) is used not *pratishat* (percentage)).
- The local procedures for solving problems of that concept need to be looked for or extracted from students.

Secondly, a way of dialogue that brings out students' culture and language needs to be outlined. Elements of dialogue mentioned above also need to explicitly form part of the framework. These could then form a checklist and rubric for selection of examples to be incorporated when selecting examples according to variation theory. A revised framework could incorporate these aspects in a more authentic manner.